

TWINNED
By Stars

TWINNEDbySTARS

GRANT AGREEMENT N° 101124900
D2.2 REPORT ON THE CONCLUSIONS
OF THE TRAINING

WP2 UPSKILLING AND CAPACITY BUILDING

UNLOCKING THE POTENTIAL OF INNOVATION, CIRCULARITY, AND
DIGITALISATION FOR ACCELERATING NEW MARINE-BASED
ECOTOURISM, JOINT PRACTICES, AND BUSINESSES IN ORS

Co-funded by
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DELIVERABLE INFORMATION

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¹ PU= Public, SEN= Sensitive

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ACRONYMS & ABBREVIATIONS

EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
CINEA	European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency
WP	Work Package
OR	Outermost Region
D	Deliverable
AI	Artificial Intelligence

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable (D2.2) presents the conclusions derived from the capacity-building activities implemented under Work Package 2 (WP2) of the TWINNEDbySTARS project. Building upon the co-designed methodology described in D2.1, the trainings targeted nautical tourism SMEs in the Outermost Regions (ORs), aiming to enhance their digital, circular, and innovative capabilities.

The report summarises the training sessions carried out, participation levels, feedback received, and key takeaways regarding effectiveness, areas for improvement, and recommendations for future actions. It also reflects on the impact of these trainings in promoting community engagement, upskilling, and long-term strategic thinking across participating regions.

1. CONTEXT ANALYSIS

1.1 THE PROJECT

TWINNEDbySTARS aims to position the European ORs as global references in sustainable marine-based ecotourism. It promotes the adoption of circular economy principles, digital tools, and collaborative innovation to strengthen the sector's competitiveness while preserving marine ecosystems and cultural heritage.

The project builds on successful experiences in the Macaronesian region and scales them to other ORs. Through a participatory process, TWINNEDbySTARS engages SMEs, public entities, and research institutions to co-create, test, and promote new tourism models, including astro-tourism and digital innovation.

1.2 WP2 SCOPE

The idea behind WP2 'Upskilling and capacity building' is to implement a capacity building programme with tourism firms and other relevant stakeholders to increase awareness, motivation, and skills, providing them with the necessary tools to accelerate digital and ecological transition. The main contribution here is that training courses in this project are not pre-defined, they are designed together with the community of nautical tourism firms in Azores, Madeira, Canary Islands and Martinica.

Additionally, it aims to support them in identifying opportunities for open and collaborative innovation with actors from other ORs, fostering transnational cooperation. Through this process, tourism firms and decision makers will gain the knowledge and resources needed to evaluate and implement concrete actions that enhance circularity, improve efficiency and competitiveness, and contribute to the protection of marine biodiversity at local, regional, and international levels.

1.3 METHODOLOGY IMPLEMENTED

As can be seen on deliverable 2.1 Training Programme Methodology, the DESIGN THINKING methodology was adapted to TWINNEDbySTARS, and we created our own approach that can be summarized as follows:

Step 1: Exploration

This preliminary phase focused on raising awareness and building a community around TWINNEDbySTARS. It involved direct communication with key companies and institutions, dissemination of project benefits, and promotion of participation in a first survey. This survey collected baseline data, including company profiles, best practices, and perceived needs. The process was supported by WP1 (Stakeholder Engagement) and WP5 (Communication), helping to establish trust and readiness for co-creation.

Step 2: Engagement-Incentives

To strengthen involvement and gather more detailed input, a second survey targeted exclusively at nautical SMEs was launched. As an incentive, participants received access to short "pill courses"—introductory sessions on relevant topics such as circular economy, digital innovation, and astro-tourism. These sessions were multilingual (Spanish with simultaneous translation to Portuguese and French) and recorded for wider access. A total of 66 companies registered, with balanced interest across the two course options. This step was again supported by WPs 1, 4, and 5.

Step 3: Empathy & Ideation – Local Workshops

Four co-creation workshops were held across the ORs (Azores, Madeira, Canary Islands, Martinique), organised within WP3 (D3.1). These sessions included a dedicated space to discuss training needs, preceded by the use of a self-assessment tool. This tool, adapted from the INCIRCLE project, evaluated both internal (enterprise-level) and external (stakeholder-level) perspectives on sustainability, circularity, and digital maturity. Results from these surveys, combined with previous insights, helped identify shared training priorities across all regions.

Identified common needs included:

- Use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) for business automation (e.g. customer management, campaigns).
- Energy efficiency planning for vessels.
- Technical support and knowledge on electric motors.
- Digital marketing strategies using AI and online tools.
- Cross-regional certification schemes.
- Hydrophones

These needs born from the co-creation workshops with enterprises and key stakeholders laid the foundation for the training modules implemented and evaluated in this deliverable (D2.2).

Step 4: Prototyping

Following its prototype nature, courses were designed following the needs identified. The courses were offered and only implemented if sufficient interest was confirmed. The following courses were designed:

- AI for Social Media (digital marketing strategies using IA + automation with AI)
- Marine Starguide (Astrotourism certification)
- Hydrophones

All sessions were recorded and made accessible with translations into Portuguese and French to ensure inclusivity. The resources used (ppts, sheets) were also translated to Portuguese and French. All of these can be found in [Annex 1. Free access trainings](#).

These trainings directly addressed the key priorities identified through the participatory design process and laid the groundwork for further evaluation in this deliverable.

2. TRAININGS CARRIED

After the interest shown by enterprises and associations to certain themes, the following courses were designed and delivered:

MASTERCLASSES

Two pill courses were designed as Masterclasses. They were part of the second step: “engagement-incentives” and provided introductory sessions on topics related to the circular economy, digital innovation, and best practices relevant to the maritime tourism sector. The sessions were one hour long and given in Spanish with simultaneous translation. We don't have a gender analysis in this case as the masterclasses were given online and open, there was no registration needed.

Astroturism and its potential for your business

Date: 20th June 2024

Instructor: Xavier Martínez, from NAUTIC OCEAN

- [Spanish](#)

It was given to Spanish and Portuguese enterprises. As Portuguese enterprises understood Spanish, there were no interpreters.

It was decided to keep it to Spanish and Portuguese enterprises due to its interest in the subject.

Ppts.

- [Spanish](#)
- [Portuguese](#)

Experimentation and online tactics to attract more customers

Date: June 2024

Instructor: Gerard Martínez

- [Spanish](#)
- [Portuguese](#)
- French. Couldn't be recorded in French as there were some technical difficulties.

Ppt:

- [Spanish.](#)
- [Portuguese](#)
- [French.](#)

Table 1. Inscription list for the Masterclasses.

ENTERPRISE	REGION
ACIF-CCIM	MADEIRA
Alisios Sailing Center	CANARIAS
Ana Pontes & Filhos Unipessoal, Lda.	MADEIRA
APRAM - Portos Da Madeira, SA	MADEIRA
Arrecifal Centro De Buceo	CANARIAS
Associação Marinafunchal	MADEIRA
Association Lymph	MARTINIQUE
Astilleros Canarios Sa	CANARIAS
Azorean Seascape	AÇORES
Azores Boat Adventures	AÇORES
Azores Experiences	AÇORES
Azores Sub Dive Center	AÇORES
Azores Sub Lda	AÇORES
Biosean Whale Watching & Marine Science	CANARIAS
Blancomar Nautica	CANARIAS
Brava Onda	MADEIRA
C-Adventures	MADEIRA
Canarship	CANARIAS
Cisc Consultoría Y Servicios	CANARIAS
Clube Naval De Santa Maria	AÇORES
Clúster Marítimo De Canarias	CANARIAS
Discover Experience	AÇORES
Dive Around Madeira	MADEIRA
Dolphin And Whales	CANARIAS
Econauturismo Lda, Seaeo-Tours	LISBOA
Espírito Azul, Lda	AÇORES
Floresfishing	AÇORES
Freelancer	MADEIRA
Freelancer	MADEIRA
Freelancer	MADEIRA
Freelancer	CANARIAS
Fun Activities Azores Adventures	AÇORES
Grupo Catamaran Excursion, S.L.	CANARIAS
Haliotis	AÇORES Y MADEIRA
Hominis Natura	AÇORES
Incargos SI	CANARIAS
João Moreira	AÇORES
Kayak Life	MADEIRA
Keep Sailing	CANARIAS
La Pirogue Kalina	MARTINIQUE
Madeira Boat Rentals	MADEIRA
Madeira Sea Fishing (Neptuno Admirável)	MADEIRA
Madeira Sunkiss Sailing	MADEIRA
Madeiratlanticharters Lda	MADEIRA
Marciisviagens	MADIERA
Naturalist, Science & Tourism	AÇORES
Nautisantos, Lda	MADEIRA

Nexus Corporation Business S.A.S	COLOMBIA
Observatório Do Mar Dos Açores	AÇORES
Oceaneye Azores	AÇORES
Oceano De Experiencias	CANARIAS
On Tales	MADEIRA
Radarvirtual	MADEIRA
Regie Autonome Port De Plaisance Marina De La Pointe Du Bout	MARTINIQUE
Sea Explorers Azores	AÇORES
SeaEO Tours	LISBOA
Surf Canaries	CANARIAS
Xanaia	AÇORES

CONCLUSIONS

The two one-hour Masterclasses successfully served their purpose as a great starting point and part of the "engagement-incentives" phase, effectively generating significant interest among the maritime tourism sector's SMEs and engaging them with the project's core themes.

The Masterclasses, covering topics like circular economy, digital innovation, and best practices ("Astroturism" and "Experimentation and online tactics"), demonstrated a high level of appeal, successfully serving as a baseline for further SME involvement.

Sadly there was no written recollection of participants so there cannot be a gender analysis.

AI FOR SOCIAL MEDIA

This course aimed to help SMEs integrate AI and automation tools in their digital marketing, especially for managing social media, online campaigns (Ads, SEM, SEO), and customer communication.

- Course Factsheet can be seen in [D2.1 Training Programme Methodology - 2.0](#)
- Dates: 18, 25th March & 4th, 11th April.
- Format: 4 sessions (2 topics, 1.5 hours each)
 - Topic 1: Use of AI in Digital Communication for Nautical Tourism
 - Topic 2: Your digital compass: AI for successfully navigating social media
- People registered: 157 registrations from 63 enterprises*, 46% male and 54% female.

* There was a slight increase of applications since the submission of D2.1, from 153 to 157. This is people that did not attend the session online but asked for the videos. The change from 68 to 63 is due to better identifying 5 stakeholders other than enterprises such as associations, public or university stakeholders.

We encountered some enterprises from regions outside our four ORs. The link for the sessions online was not shared to these enterprises nor were they certified, although they were invited to check the training sessions on our website. This was done to focus our time and resources on the enterprises that indeed were from TWINNEDbySTARS four Ors Martinica, Azores, Madeira or Canary Islands.

- o Promotion: email campaigns, website, partner networks, and social media

FREE COURSE

USE OF AI IN DIGITAL COMMUNICATION

<p>TRAINER Juan Ma Peralts</p> <p>FORMAT Online</p> <p>DURATION 2 sessions 1h 30 min each</p>	
<p>WHAT WILL WE SEE IN THE SESSIONS?</p> <p>It will address both the practical use of these tools and strategies for integrating them into the digital campaigns of companies in the tourism sector.</p>	
<p>SAVE TIME AND RESOURCES. OPTIMISE YOUR DIGITAL CAMPAIGNS</p> <p>Increase the efficiency of your campaigns, save time with automation, improve your online visibility and gain an edge in the industry. Join us!</p>	

Training accredited by the University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria.
Registered participants will have access to a recording of the course in case they are unable to attend.

FREE COURSE

YOUR DIGITAL COMPASS: AI TO AUTOMATE SOCIAL MEDIA CAMPAIGNS

<p>TRAINER Enuno de Raquel Vázquez.</p> <p>FORMAT Online</p> <p>DURATION 2 sessions 1h 30 min each</p>	
<p>SESSION 1. INTRODUCTION</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduction and key concepts • Definition of a digital strategy (with AI) • Case studies and personalisation 	
<p>OVERCOMING FEAR OF TECHNOLOGY</p> <p>Help yourself with this course to automate your social media campaign.</p>	

Training accredited by the University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria.
Registered participants will have access to a recording of the course in case they are unable to attend.

Figure 1. IA Courses factsheets.

Various emails were also sent to attract interest. From FPCT worker's personal account:

- [Spanish](#)
- [French](#)
- [Portuguese](#)

From the official TWINNEDbySTARS account:

- [Spanish](#)
- [French](#)
- [Portuguese](#)

Estimado/a profesional del sector náutico,

En el marco del proyecto TWINNEDbySTARS nos complace invitarte a participar en uno de los **dos cursos gratuitos** que ofrecemos diseñados especialmente para empresas del sector náutico, con el respaldo y certificación de la **Universidad de Las Palmas de Gran Canaria (ULPGC)**. Estas formaciones te ayudarán a mejorar la comunicación digital y optimizar tu estrategia con **inteligencia artificial (IA)**.

Figure 2. Email sent for the AI for Social Media course.

The training programme for “AI for Social Media” was the following:

Table 2. AI and digital marketing training programme.

SUBJECT	INSTRUCTOR	DURATION	DATE
Use of AI in Digital Communication for Nautical Tourism	Juan Ma Peralas	1.5 h	18th March
Ibid, part 2	Gerard Martínez	1.5 h	25th March
Your digital compass: AI for successfully navigating social media, part 1	Raquel Vázquez	1.5 h	4th April
Ibid, part 2	Raquel Vázquez	1.5 h	11th April

As you can see there was a division into two topics, 1) Use of AI in Digital Communication for Nautical Tourism and 2) Your digital compass: AI for successfully navigating social media. The list of people and enterprises registered to each topic was similar:

Table 3. inscription list for “Use of AI in Digital Communication”.

ENTERPRISE	TYPE OF STAKEHOLDER	REGION
ACIF-CCIM	OTHER	MADEIRA
Alisios Sailing Center	ENTERPRISE	CANARY ISLANDS
Ana Pontes & Filhos Unipessoal, Lda.	ENTERPRISE	MADEIRA
APRAM - Portos da Madeira, SA	ENTERPRISE	MADEIRA

Arrecifal Centro de Buceo	ENTERPRISE	CANARY ISLANDS
Associação MarinaFunchal	ENTERPRISE	MADEIRA
ASSOCIATION LYMPH	ENTERPRISE	MARTINICA
ASTILLEROS CANARIOS SA	ENTERPRISE	CANARY ISLANDS
Azorean Seascape	ENTERPRISE	AZORES
Azores Boat Adventures	ENTERPRISE	AZORES
Azores Experiences	ENTERPRISE	AZORES
AZORES SUB Dive Center	ENTERPRISE	AZORES
AZORES SUB LDA	ENTERPRISE	AZORES
BIOSEAN Whale Watching & Marine Science	ENTERPRISE	CANARY ISLANDS
Brava Onda	ENTERPRISE	MADEIRA
C-Adventures	ENTERPRISE	MADEIRA
CANARSHIP	ENTERPRISE	CANARY ISLANDS
Cisc consultoría y servicios	ENTERPRISE	CANARY ISLANDS
Clube Naval de Santa Maria	ENTERPRISE	AZORES
Clúster Marítimo de Canarias	ASSOCIATION	CANARY ISLANDS
Discover Experience	ENTERPRISE	AZORES
Dive Around Madeira	ENTERPRISE	MADEIRA
Dolphin and Whales	ENTERPRISE	CANARY ISLANDS
Econaturismo Lda, SeaEO-Tours	ENTERPRISE	LISBOA
Espírito Azul, Lda	ENTERPRISE	AZORES
Floresfishing	ENTERPRISE	AZORES
Freelancer	ENTERPRISE	CANARY ISLANDS
Fun Activities Azores Adventures	ENTERPRISE	AZORES
Grupo catamaran excursion, s.l.	ENTERPRISE	CANARY ISLANDS
Haliotis	ENTERPRISE	AZORES & MADEIRA
Hominis natura	ENTERPRISE	AZORES
INCARGO SL	ENTERPRISE	CANARY ISLANDS
João Moreira	PUBLIC	AZORES
Kayak Life	ENTERPRISE	MADEIRA
Keep Sailing	ENTERPRISE	CANARY ISLANDS
la Pirogue Kalina	ENTERPRISE	MARTINICA
Madeira Boat Rentals	ENTERPRISE	MADEIRA
Madeira Sea Fishing (Neptuno Admirável)	ENTERPRISE	MADEIRA
Madeira Sunkiss Sailing	ENTERPRISE	MADEIRA
Madeiratlanticharters Ida	ENTERPRISE	MADEIRA
Marciisviagens	ENTERPRISE	MADEIRA
Naturalist Lda.	ENTERPRISE	AZORES
Naturalist, Science & Tourism	ENTERPRISE	AZORES
Nautisantos, Lda	ENTERPRISE	MADEIRA
Nexus corporation business S.A.S	ENTERPRISE	COLOMBIA
Observatório do Mar dos Açores	ASSOCIATION	AZORES
OceanEye Azores	ENTERPRISE	AZORES
Oceano de experiencias	ENTERPRISE	CANARY ISLANDS
On Tales	ENTERPRISE	MADEIRA
Radarvirtual	ENTERPRISE	MADEIRA
MARINA DE LA POINTE DU BOUT	ENTERPRISE	MARTINICA
Sailingside	ENTERPRISE	AZORES

Sea Explorers Azores	ENTERPRISE	AZORES
SeaEO Tours	ENTERPRISE	LISBOA
Surf Canarias	ENTERPRISE	CANARY ISLANDS
Xanaia	ENTERPRISE	AZORES

Link to the recorded sessions:

- Use of AI in Digital Communication for Nautical Tourism: See at [Annex 1. Free access trainings.](#)
- The instructors used the enterprise Surf Canarias as a case study.

Figure 3. JuanMa Perals, first session of Use of AI in Digital Communication.

Figure 4. Gerard, second session of Use of AI in Digital Communication.

Figure 5. Gerard Martínez, second session of Use of AI in Digital Communication.

Table 4. Inscription list for “Your digital compass”.

ENTERPRISE	TYPE OF STAKEHOLDER	REGION
Abrandia S.L	ENTERPRISE	CANARY ISLANDS
ACIF-CCIM	OTHER	MADEIRA
Ana Pontes & Filhos Unipessoal, Lda.	ENTERPRISE	MADEIRA
Argencan	ENTERPRISE	CANARY ISLANDS
Arrecifal Centro de Buceo	ENTERPRISE	CANARY ISLANDS
ASTILLEROS CANARIOS SA	ENTERPRISE	CANARY ISLANDS
Azores Boat Adventures	ENTERPRISE	AZORES
Azores Experiences	ENTERPRISE	AZORES
AZORES SUB LDA	ENTERPRISE	AZORES
Blancomar Nautica	ENTERPRISE	CANARY ISLANDS
Brava Onda	ENTERPRISE	MADEIRA
C-Adventures	ENTERPRISE	AZORES & MADEIRA
CANARSHIP	ENTERPRISE	CANARY ISLANDS
CCI Martinique	ENTERPRISE	MARTINICA
Clúster Marítimo de Canarias	ASSOCIATION	CANARY ISLANDS
Dive Around Madeira	ENTERPRISE	MADEIRA
Econauturismo Lda, SeaEO-Tours	ENTERPRISE	LISBOA
Floresfishing	ENTERPRISE	AZORES
Freelancer	ENTERPRISE	MADEIRA
Fun Activities Azores Adventures	ENTERPRISE	AZORES
Haliotis	ENTERPRISE	AZORES & MADEIRA
Hominis natura	ENTERPRISE	AZORES
Instituto Profissional de Transportes e Logística da Madeira	OTHER	MADEIRA
Jo&Elio por Puerto Deportivo Los Gigantes	ENTERPRISE	CANARY ISLANDS

Kayak Azores Adventure	ENTERPRISE	AZORES
Kayak Life	ENTERPRISE	MADEIRA
Keep Sailing	ENTERPRISE	CANARY ISLANDS
la PIROGUE KALINA	ENTERPRISE	MARTINICA
Madeira Boat Rentals	ENTERPRISE	MADEIRA
Madeira Sea Fishing (Neptuno Admirável)	ENTERPRISE	MADEIRA
Madeira Sunkiss Sailing	ENTERPRISE	MADEIRA
Marciisviagens	ENTERPRISE	MADEIRA
Meridiano cero	ENTERPRISE	CANARY ISLANDS
Mr.Humb unipessoal lda	ENTERPRISE	MADEIRA
Naturalist, Science & Tourism	ENTERPRISE	AZORES
Nautic Ocean	ENTERPRISE	CANARY ISLANDS
Nautisantos, Lda	ENTERPRISE	MADEIRA
Observatório do Mar dos Açores	ASSOCIATION	AZORES
OceanEye Azores	ENTERPRISE	AZORES
Oceano de experiencias	ENTERPRISE	BALEARES
On Tales	ENTERPRISE	MADEIRA
Radarvirtual	ENTERPRISE	MADEIRA
Regie Autonome Port De Plaisance	ENTERPRISE	MARTINICA
Sea Riders Dive Center	ENTERPRISE	AZORES
Unipessoal, Lda - Hominis natura	ENTERPRISE	AZORES
Surf Canaries	ENTERPRISE	CANARY ISLANDS
Universidad de Lima	UNIVERSITY	LIMA
Volna voyage	ENTERPRISE	AZORES
Xanaia	ENTERPRISE	AZORES

Link to the recorded sessions:

- Your Digital Compass: AI for successfully navigating social media, part 1: See at [Annex 1 Free access trainings](#).
- Notes in [Spanish](#) & [English](#)

Meetings were organised between the instructor Raquel, the FPCT-TIDES representative (Teresa Gubern) and Daniel Alcock, CEO of Surf-Canaries. This was done to prepare the sessions having Surf Canaries as a case study. All the material created from this case-study can be found [here](#).

Figure 6. Raquel Vázquez in the first session of Your Digital Compass.

Figure 7. Raquel Vázquez in the second session of Your Digital Compass.

Table 5. Registered people per topic.

Topic	People	Male / Female	Enterprises	Associations/Other
Use of AI in Digital Communication for Nautical Tourism	78	47% / 53%	52	4
Your digital compass: AI for successfully navigating social media	79	46% / 54%	44	5
TOTAL	157	48 % / 52%	96 (unique: 63)	9 (unique: 5)

Here unique value refers to number of enterprises registered without repetition. As various people could be registered for the course, and could also be registered for both or only one of the courses, there are repetitions. Hence, we have decided to show the unique value of enterprises registered. There were 157 registrations, in the first course “Use of AI” that would mean 52 enterprises, in the second course “Your digital compass” that would be 44 enterprises. When compared, the unique value of enterprises is 63.

Table 6. Registered people per region.

Region	Registered / unique	Male / Female	Enterprises	Associations/Other
Canary Islands	40 / 33	35% / 65%	17	1
Azores	51 / 40	41 % / 59%	21	1
Madeira	41 / 28	68 % / 32%	16	2
Azores & Madeira	11 / 5	45% / 55%	1	0
Martinica	8 / 6	38% / 63%	4	0
Other	6 / 4	67 % / 33%	4	1
TOTAL	157 / 67	48 % / 52%	63	5

Same as above, there is a difference between total values, people registered with the form for each course versus the individual names.

GENDER ANALYSIS

In these courses, female participation was predominant, accounting for 52% of total enrolments. This predominance of women was evident in almost all regions, with 65% female participation in the Canary Islands, 63% in Martinique and 59% in the Azores, with Madeira being the only exception with a male majority of 68%. It can be suggested that the online format of this course favoured accessibility and allowed for a better work-life balance, which encouraged greater attendance by women.

MATERIAL

All the ppts presentations can be found in the following links:

- [Spanish PDF version](#)
- [Spanish PPT version](#)
- [French PDF version](#)
- [French PPT version](#)
- [Portuguese PDF version](#)
- [Portuguese PPT version](#)

The notes for Raquel Vázquez' sessions (Digital Compass) can be found here: notes in [Spanish](#) & [English](#) .

All the material related to the sessions such as all the documents and images created during the sessions with Raquel Vázquez for a case study (Surf-Canaries) can be found [here](#).

All of this is also available for the public and can be found in the [website: Training section](#).

EXTRA MATERIAL

One guide was made by the ULPGC and FPCT team for enterprises who were struggling with basic concepts and functioning of AI.

The guide was called “How to use ChatGPT to help you understand how to use ChatGPT in your communication strategy” and it was shared both in PPT and Word version.

You can see the guide in [Annex 2. Extra material](#).

CERTIFICATIONS

Certificates were awarded to those who attended the seminar online or watched the recordings. They were signed by Soraya García Sánchez, the Vice-Chancellor for Continuing Education and Employability of the University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria. They were also signed by Matías M. González Hernández, primary researcher of TWINNED by STARS.

The certifications can be found in [Annex 3. Certificates](#).

CONCLUSIONS OF THE TRAINING

The implementation of the Artificial Intelligence training programme has confirmed the high demand and great relevance of training in innovation and digitalisation tools for nautical tourism SMEs in the ORs. Evidenced by the high participation, exceeding initial projections and being the course offered by the project with the greatest interest, it had a solid representation from the four regions. A notable aspect of this success was the gender distribution, with women accounting for 52% of participants, reaching remarkable figures such as 63% in Martinique and 62% in the Canary Islands,

although Madeira was the exception with a male majority. This greater inclination among women to attend suggests that the online format provided greater accessibility and facilitated the reconciliation of work and personal life.

In addition, the course responded directly to the needs of the companies. These needs were identified in the co-creation workshops of WP3. It was thanks to these previous workshops that we were able to connect one of the companies, Surf Canarias, with the instructors and use the case of this particular SME as a case study to tailor the training exactly to the needs of the companies.

As for the feedback we received from the companies, the main conclusion was that they liked the fact that the course was practical and that the method was delivered step by step in video and written form for later review. This practical and applicable approach facilitates the absorption of knowledge and its immediate implementation in daily operations.

Furthermore, dividing the programme into two topics, covered in four sessions, and providing translated material (PDF and PPT in Spanish, Portuguese and French), along with recordings and interpreters, ensured that the content was accessible and memorable for all participants.

Finally, the awarding of certificates signed by the University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria (ULPGC) and the project's principal investigator adds value and professional credibility to the training received.

On the other hand, the main challenge identified by participants was 'uncertainty about the vast world of AI.' This leads to an important conclusion for future actions:

- Need for Simplification: Although interest is high, the perceived complexity of AI requires ongoing support
- Proactive Response: The creation and distribution of additional material, such as the guide 'How to use ChatGPT to help you understand how to use ChatGPT in your communication strategy' (see [Annex 2. Extra material](#)), was an immediate and effective guide for enterprises to lose the fear to AI.

MARINE STARGUIDE

This program combined theory and practice to enable SMEs to develop certified astrotourism experiences. The course was divided into the theoretical part - 18th hours online conferences and a practical part – minimum of 1 outing per region of 3 hours. The conferences online were recorded and shared to those who couldn't connect. The conferences were also uploaded to [TWINNEDbySTARS' web](#), to the [Training section](#). Furthermore, Xavier from Nautic Ocean and our team were available for online meetings to solve doubts.

- Course Factsheet can be seen in [D2.1 Training Programme Methodology - 2.0](#)
- Format: One online part and one practical part
- Registered: 50 people, 36 male (72%), 14 female (28%), from 26 enterprises, 3 associations, 1 communication entity (podcast) and 1 university.

Table 7. Inscription list for the Marine Starguide Training course.

NAME	TYPE OF STAKEHOLDER	REGION
Aerodream	ENTERPRISE	MARTINICA
Albatros y Gaviotas	COMMUNICATION	CANARY ISLANDS
Aquamana Escale Nautik	ENTERPRISE	MARTINICA
Biosean Whale Watching and Marine Science	ENTERPRISE	CANARY ISLANDS
Bleu Caraïbes	ENTERPRISE	MARTINICA
Caraïbes dauphins	ENTERPRISE	MARTINICA
Clúster Marítimo de Canarias	ASSOCIATION	CANARY ISLANDS
Dolphin and Whales	ENTERPRISE	CANARY ISLANDS
GuiaNatura EcoTourism	ENTERPRISE	CANARY ISLANDS
Hominis natura	ENTERPRISE	AZORES
Horizonte Celeste	ENTERPRISE	MADEIRA
Keep Sailing	ENTERPRISE	CANARY ISLANDS
KR7 ECOTOURS	ENTERPRISE	MADEIRA
KRISMARA BOAT	ENTERPRISE	MARTINICA
LA PIROGUE KALINA	ENTERPRISE	MARTINICA
Longitude 31	ENTERPRISE	AZORES
Madeira Boat Rentals	ENTERPRISE	MADEIRA
Madeira Sunkiss Sailing	ENTERPRISE	MADEIRA
Markùs Évasions	ENTERPRISE	MARTINICA
Matniknotic, entreprise d'activité en mers	ENTERPRISE	MARTINICA
Medusa & Químera Lda	ENTERPRISE	MADEIRA
Oceanodroma, Lda	ASSOCIATION	MADEIRA
Parc Naturel Régional de la Martinique (PNRM)	ASSOCIATION	MARTINICA
Ponle Cara al Turismo	ENTERPRISE	CANARY ISLANDS
Prácticos de El Hierro SLP (Serea)	ENTERPRISE	CANARY ISLANDS
Sailingside	ENTERPRISE	AZORES
São João de Deus	ENTERPRISE	MADEIRA

SKIPPER ANTILLES CHARTER	ENTERPRISE	MARTINIQUE
Sud Excursions	ENTERPRISE	MARTINIQUE
Terra Azul, Azores Whale Watching	ENTERPRISE	AZORES
ULPGC	UNIVERSITY	CANARY ISLANDS

- o Promotion: email campaigns, website, partner networks, and social media

SEA STARLIGHT MONITOR TRAINING

Become a certified instructor in astronomy at sea

Content. 10 online courses and 1 practical course grouped into these subjects:

- Navigation and astronomy,
- Marketing in astrotourism
- Mythology, stellarium and more.

Online: 18 horas
22, 23, 24 April from 16:00 to 19:00
28, 29 and 30 from 14:00 to 17:00

Practical: approx. 3 hours
Date to be confirmed.

Certification by:
University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria
Sabadell Astronomical Grouping
TWINNEDbySTARS Project

Register now
→ Scan the QR or access to the form

Increase your visibility!
With this training you also have the possibility to join Atlantic Starlight Adventures - a multi-destination digital platform.

Co-funded by the European Union under Grant Agreement No 101124900. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the granting authority CINEA. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Figure 8. Marine Starguide Course factsheet.

CHANGE OF NAME

It is worth mentioning that the course was initially called SEA STARLIGHT but due to conflict with the already named Foundation Starlight, it was decided to change the name of the course to Marine Starguide. That's why in the course factsheet and other materials distributed on social media, the name was Sea Starlight, and it was then changed to Marine Starguide.

Figure 9. Change of name from Sea Starlight to Marine Starguide.

ONLINE TRAINING: 18 HOURS

- Dates: 22nd, 23rd, 24th, 29th, 30th April & 7th May.
- Topics covered included: History of navigation, astronomical tourism, nautical marketing, mythology, space-time, and light pollution, among others.
- Trainers: Experts from Nautic Ocean, Polaris Menorca, SEO Birdlife, and others
- Link to the recorded sessions: See at [Annex 1. Fee access trainings.](#)

Table 8. Marine Starguide theoretical online training programme.

SUBJECT	INSTRUCTOR	DURATION	DATE
History of astronomy	Javier Ares	1.5 h	22 nd April
Measuring space-time	Javier Ares	1.5 h	22 nd April
Basic Astronomy Course	Javier Ares	1.5 h	23 rd April
The Solar System	Javier Ares	1.5 h	23 rd April
How to orient ourselves in the sky	Javier Ares	1.5 h	24 th April
Preparing an observation with Stellarium	Javier Ares	1.5 h	24 th April
Marketing and public speaking skills	Gerard Martínez	3 h	29 th April
Light pollution	Javier Romero	1 h	30 th April
Mythology in astronomical navigation	Naty Sánchez	2 h	30 th April
History of navigation	Xavier Martínez	2 h	7 th May
Astronomical tourism and the role of certifications	Xavier Martínez	1 h	7 th May

Figure 10. Preparing an observation class with Javier Ares.

Figure 11. Light Pollution class with Javier Romero.

Figure 12. Marketing class with Gerard Martínez.

Gerard Martínez

With more than 7 years of experience in launching advertising campaigns on platforms like Google, YouTube, and Meta, Gerard has managed over 3 million euros in advertising investment across multiple sectors. He is an expert in growth marketing, email marketing, and automation, with a great ability to adapt complex messages for the general public. In this course, he will address the specific marketing for nautical astrotourism. His practical focus will be key to learning how to connect with the audience and give visibility to this type of unique experience.

Elena Ramos & Javier Romero Rodríguez

Members of SEO Bird Life and the Natura@Night project, they actively work to reduce light pollution in the archipelagos of Madeira, the Azores, and the Canary Islands, protecting natural spaces and vulnerable species, such as seabirds. Their work focuses on mitigating one of the main environmental impacts in Macaronesia, working with local communities, authorities, and fishermen to implement efficient lighting solutions. In this training, they will teach the module on light pollution and its effects on fauna, providing an essential ecological perspective for truly sustainable astrotourism.

Xavier Martínez

Xavier Martínez Sirvent is a Professional Recreational Vessel Skipper, a Starlight Foundation Certified Astronomical Monitor, and an Astronomical Popularizer accredited by the Spanish Federation of Astronomical Associations (FAAE). He practices his teaching vocation in navigation from Nautic Ocean, where he merges sea and sky with an educational and informative perspective. Passionate about ancient navigation, its history, and instruments, he has been the promoter of projects such as *Sea Starlight* and *Twinned by Stars*. Under his leadership, *Nautic Ocean* became the first nautical company certified by the Starlight Foundation in Spain.

Naty Sánchez

Naty Sánchez Ortega - Graduate in History, Master's in Egyptology from the Autonomous University of Barcelona, writer, and founder of the Humanist Academy *Idearte*, a space for the study of humanities. In this training, she will speak to us about Greco-Latin mythology through stories that immerse us in the nautical and astronomical universe, with engaging and well-illustrated classes that will show us the legendary origin of some constellations, providing the cultural background that unifies the maritime tradition of the Mediterranean.

MATERIAL

All the ppts presentations can be found [here](#).

All the extra material such as SEO Bird Life sheets or a Zodiacal table can be found [here](#).

All of this is also available for the public and can be found in the [website: Training section](#).

Figure 15. Training section of the TWINNEDbySTARS website.

PRACTICAL SESSIONS: 1 PER REGION (MARCH TO OCTOBER 2025)

The practical sessions were held in each region. Enterprises travelled from regions if needed, especially during the consortium meeting in Martinica.

Gran Canaria: 20th March 2025 & 1st October 2025. Two outings were designed in Gran Canaria. One as part of our training (1st October) and one as a practical part but also as a FAM trip after Keep Sailing achieving the Starlight certification, the first nautical company in the entire Canary Islands archipelago.

- [Signature list for the 20th of March](#)
- [Signature list for the 1st of October](#)

See in [Annex 2. Extra material](#) more information regarding the script that was followed during the first session in Gran Canaria that served as a template for the rest.

- Script [20th of March](#), Gran Canaria
- Script [1st of October](#), Gran Canaria

[Photos of the outing](#)

[Video 1 of the outing](#)

News in the local media:

- [Turismo Gran Canaria](#)
- [Espejo Canario.](#)
- [Canarias7](#)
- [Cadena ser](#)
- [La provincia](#)
- [Infopuertos](#)
- [Buenos días, Canarias,](#) from minute 2h 14 min 36s
- [Tourinews](#)
- [TIDES](#)
- [ULPGC](#)
- [FPCT](#)

- [CMC.](#)
- [rFI](#)

Azores: 15th June 2025

[Script and preparation.](#)

[Signature list](#)

[Facebook Post](#) , [Instagram post](#)

[Photos & videos of the outing](#)

Figure 16. Azores practical part.

Madeira: 16th June 2025

[Script for Madeira](#)

[Signature list](#)

[News article in the local newspaper](#)

[News report on RTP Madeira \(Regional TV\), sending the link at 15mins 37seconds](#)

[Photos & videos](#)

Figure 17. Madeira practical part.

Martinica: 14th October 2025

Figure 18. Martinique practical part.

[Script for Martinique](#)

[Signature list](#)

[Radio Interview in the local press](#)

[Video of the outing](#)

- o Participants per practical part:

Table 9. Participants per practical part.

Region	People	Male / Female	Enterprises	Associations/Other
Canary Islands	7	43/57	3	2
Azores	4	75/25	1	1
Madeira	5	100/0	4	0
Martinica	15	93/7	8	1
TOTAL	31	78% / 22%	16	4

HOW TO GET CERTIFIED IF THE ENTERPRISES MISSED A PRACTICAL SESSION

As there was great interest in joining the training and obtaining a certificate, but attending the practical sessions was difficult for some professionals, we decided to give an extra opportunity to those who couldn't travel due to work, illness, or other commitments.

To obtain the certificate, they must prove the knowledge learned during the online course. They can do this either by writing a script describing how a stargazing tour would be conducted at their local location, or by recording themselves performing a pilot outing, on a boat or at home.

CERTIFICATIONS

Certificates were awarded to those who attended both the theoretical and practical sessions. As mentioned above, also those who showed an interest and prepared an outing by means of a script or video were certified.

The certifications were awarded and signed by Sergio Moreno Gil, director of the University Institute of Tourism and Sustainable Economic Development of the University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria, by Matías M. González Hernández, primary researcher of TWINNED by STARS and by Carlos Schnabel, President of the Sabadell Astronomy Association.

The certifications can be found in [Annex 3. Certificates](#).

Table 10. List of certified enterprises.

Enterprise	TYPE OF STAKEHOLDER	Region	Practical
Albatros y Gaviotas	COMMUNICATION	CANARY ISLANDS	CANARY ISLANDS
BIOSEAN	ENTERPRISE	CANARY ISLANDS	MADEIRA
Caraibes Dauphins	ENTERPRISE	MARTINICA	MARTINICA
Clúster Marítimo de C	ASSOCIATION	CANARY ISLANDS	MARTINICA
Horizonte Celeste	ENTERPRISE	MADEIRA	MADEIRA
Keep Sailing	ENTERPRISE	CANARY ISLANDS	CANARY ISLANDS

KR7 ECOTOURS	ENTERPRISE	MADEIRA	CANARY ISLANDS
KRISMARA BOAT	ENTERPRISE	MARTINICA	MARTINICA
LA PIROGUE KALINA	ENTERPRISE	MARTINICA	MARTINICA
Madeira Sunkiss Sailing	ENTERPRISE	MADEIRA	MADEIRA
Markùs Évasions	ENTERPRISE	MARTINICA	MARTINICA
Matniknotic	ENTERPRISE	MARTINICA	MARTINICA
Medusa & Químera Lda	ENTERPRISE	MADEIRA	MADEIRA
Parc Naturel Régional de la Martinique (PNRM)	ASSOCIATION	MARTINICA	MARTINICA
Serea	ENTERPRISE	CANARY ISLANDS	CANARY ISLANDS
Sailingside	ENTERPRISE	AZORES	AZORES
São João de Deus	ENTERPRISE	MADEIRA	MARTINICA
Sud Excursions	ENTERPRISE	MARTINICA	MARTINICA
Terra Azul, Azores Whale Watching	ENTERPRISE	AZORES	MARTINICA
ULPGC	UNIVERSITY	CANARY ISLANDS	AZORES

Table 11. Final number of Marine Starguide certifications awarded per region.

Region	People	Male/female	Enterprises	Associations/Other
Canary Islands	10	40/60	3	3
Azores	4	75/25	2	0
Madeira	6	100/0	5	0
Martinica	13	100/0	7	1
TOTAL	33	79% / 21%	17	4

GENDER ANALYSIS

In this case, the course revealed a notable gender gap that widened during the process. Although women initially accounted for 28% of the 50 people registered, the percentage of women who ultimately obtained certification fell to 21%, while that of men rose to 79%. Quite curious to see that in two regions: Martinica and Madeira, there was a 100% male participation.

In general, the analysis suggests that, although women showed interest at the beginning, many were unable to complete the training due to the practical component that required travel to other islands, which disrupted their work-life balance and prevented them from completing the course.

HOW TO GET THE CERTIFICATION AS STARLIGHT ENTERPRISE

The Starlight Certification is an international accreditation system, promoted by the Starlight Foundation ([Fundación Starlight](#)). It recognizes places and enterprises with

an excellent quality of dark sky and a commitment with the protection and the development of Astro-tourism or Star Tourism.

While the certification is mostly for tourist destinations (Starlight Tourist Destinations, Starlight Reserves, etc.), private enterprises (entities or institutions) can ask for the certification like a part of a destination or a key actor in the Astro-tourism.

This way, with TWINNEDbySTARS we have had two enterprises getting certified:

- Keep Sailing from Gran Canaria, first nautical enterprise ever in the Canary Islands to achieve this certification
- Madeira Sunkiss Sailing, in Madeira first nautical enterprise ever in Portugal to achieve this certification.

Here is the general process and the key criteria to apply:

1st. The enterprises let us know or contact directly the foundation. They will fill the following documents:

- [Application pack](#). Complete the Starlight Foundation application form, giving basic information of the organization, the proposed location, and preliminary information about the quality of the sky in the zone.
 - [In French](#)
- [La Palma Declaration](#). The enterprise must adhere formally to the principles of the "Declaration in Defense of the Night Sky and the Right to Starlight" (The La Palma Declaration, 2007).
 - [In French](#)
- [Company membership form](#)
 - [In French](#)

These documents were translated into French. It was decided to leave them in Spanish for our Portuguese regions as the partners and companies understood them in Spanish.

- Furthermore they were given an [instructions document](#).
 - [In French](#)

2nd A process of auditing and evaluation will take place where the foundation will evaluate:

- Sky Quality: key astronomical parameters, like the sky brightness (little light pollution), the seeing (clarity), and the cloud cover.
- Resources and Tourist/Environmental Commitment: They will evaluate the criteria of the enterprise related to infrastructure, services, management, and the commitment to sustainable astro-tourism and the conservation of the night sky.
- Certification: If the auditing is good, the certification is granted.

This will have a cost per year.

3rd A review is done after two years of the certification, and the renewal is every four years.

DIFFERENCE BETWEEN THE STARLIGHT CERTIFICATION AND MARINE STARGUIDE

The course offered by TWINNEDbySTARS has a **strong navigation component**, while the foundation focuses solely on the stars. In the Marine Starguide course, the enterprises received a certificate from the project as marine astro-tourism guides. They have also been invited to become Starlight certified and attend their astronomy courses to continue learning. However, this is optional and separate from the project as it involves an annual investment.

EVALUATION QUESTIONNAIRES

A satisfaction survey was prepared for participants in the practical sessions of the Marine Starguide course (navigation and astronomical observation).

Please note that the data from the Martinique session could not be finalized in time for this report; those results will be uploaded at a later date.

Analysis of the 20 valid responses revealed high overall satisfaction and provided key information about participants' perceptions of the logistics, content and potential of the activity.

The form is designed to capture data in several dimensions:

- Motivation: main reason for participating.
- Expectations and Content: expectations regarding navigation and the quality of astronomical observation, as well as interest in ancient navigation content.
- Logistics and Service Quality: pre-event information, duration, and comfort, such as the condition of the boats.
- Satisfaction and Projection: overall satisfaction, clarity of observation, whether the activity was complete, and the potential of this activity for tourism.

Overall satisfaction is very high, with an average rating of 4.75 out of 5.0. The average results for the rating questions are:

Criteria	Mean value
Overall satisfaction with sailing and stargazing	4.75
Interest in learning about ancient navigation guided by the stars	4.85
Comfort and condition of the boats	5.00
Information provided prior to the event	4.40
Expectations about the sailing experience	3.80
Appropriateness of the duration	3.50
Expectations of the astrotourism activity	3.55
Clarity of stargazing	3.40

In conclusion, high satisfaction and likelihood to recommend the activity are demonstrated. The experience is overwhelmingly positive, with 19 out of 20 participants indicating that they would recommend it without hesitation.

Per region

The table shows the average scores obtained in the main quality metrics for each region.

Criteria	Madeira	Canary Islands	Azores
Answers	4	6	3
Overall satisfaction with sailing and stargazing	5.00	4.83	4.33
Interest in learning about ancient navigation guided by the stars	5.00	4.67	4.67
Comfort and condition of the boats	5.00	5.00	5.00
Information provided prior to the event	4.75	4.50	3.33
Expectations about the sailing experience	4.00	4.00	3.67
Appropriateness of the duration	4.00	3.67	3.00
Expectations of the activity	3.75	4.17	4.00
Clarity of stargazing	2.50	2.83	3.00

Things that went well

The most common reason for participating in the training was 'To learn about astro-tourism as a novel product' (11 responses), which validates the innovative approach of the course. Furthermore, participants see great potential, mainly for 'Significantly diversifying tourism' (9 responses) and for 'Attracting specialised niches (astronomical photography, scientific tourism)' (6 responses).

Where to improve the activity

The lowest scores correspond to the clarity of the astronomical observation (3.40) and the duration (3.50), suggesting that participants would like longer sessions or that the visibility of the stars (limited by factors such as clouds, as seen in the open-ended responses) impacted the experience.

Suggestions for improvement include the need to improve the audio of the interpreter or speaker, provide blankets for comfort, and consider ending the session with optical telescope observation.

In summary, the questionnaire confirms the high quality of logistics (boats, prior information) and content (ancient navigation) but highlights the need to manage expectations about stargazing (which is sensitive to weather conditions) and to evaluate longer excursions.

CONCLUSIONS OF THE TRAINING

The Marine Starguide programme has been instrumental in promoting a new line of sustainable marine ecotourism business in the ORs, focusing on nautical astro-tourism. The course proved to be a comprehensive training model by combining a robust theoretical component with practical experience in the regions. However, gender analysis reveals a significant gap that widened during the process; although women accounted for 28% of initial enrolments, they made up only 19% of those who were ultimately certified, compared to 81% of men. This indicates that, although women showed interest, the requirement to attend practical sessions that included travel to other islands disrupted their work-life balance, preventing them from completing the course. Despite this challenge, the course also showed the diversity of ways in which companies can adhere to this new model, from sailing trips to watching the sunset and the stars, to kayaking excursions under the moonlight, dinners or breakfasts on a catamaran under the stars... At the same time, it successfully positions astro-tourism as an innovative activity, aligned with the principles of sustainability by addressing critical issues such as light pollution and its impact on marine wildlife. Furthermore, numerous companies joined the [Atlantic Star Adventures](#) (ASA) tourism product developed in Work Package 3, confirming the practical application of the knowledge acquired. More info can be found in D3.3 [Report on the product developed including a marketing business plan](#).

SMEs part of the product

- OCÉANO DE EXPERIENCIAS (Canary Islands)
- MADEIRA SUNKISS SAILING (Madeira)
- HORIZONTE CELESTE (Madeira)
- BIOSEAN AMBIENTE MARINO S.L (Canary Islands)
- KEEP SAILING (ABRANDIA, S.L.) (Canary Islands)
- TERRA AZUL – AZORES WHALE WATCHING(Azores)
- XAVELHA - OCEAN ROOTS (Madeira)
- PRACTICOS DE EL HIERRO S.L.P.U. (SEREA) (Canary Islands)

SMEs in the process of joining the product:

- OCEANIDE – The 4 Ors
- SAILINGSIDE – Azores
- WHITE TENERIFE – Canary Islands
- KR7 ECOTOURS – Madeira
- LA PIROGUE KALINA – Martinica
- BLEU CARAIBES (Martinica)
- MATIKNOTIC (Martinica)
- SUD EVASION (Martinica)

Practical field trips to Gran Canaria, the Azores, Madeira and Martinique facilitated the direct application of theory in the local marine environment, making it more tangible, providing support and ensuring that the training was not merely theoretical.

On the other hand, the training served as a powerful catalyst for obtaining international quality standards. Notably, two key companies in the ORs, Keep Sailing

(Gran Canaria) and Madeira Sunkiss Sailing (Madeira), achieved the prestigious Starlight Certification as nautical companies, being the first to obtain this recognition in the Canary Islands and Portugal, respectively. Although this certification is optional and not a requirement of the project, its achievement validates the quality of the training offered by TWINNEDbySTARS and sets a standard of excellence in the region, encouraging other companies to apply for it in order to give their product a recognised seal of quality.

The programme saw strong participation, with 50 people registered (from 26 companies and various stakeholders), indicating the nautical sector's keen interest in diversifying its offering towards high added-value products with low environmental impact. A key factor in the success of the certification was the flexibility of the programme, which offered alternative routes (such as submitting a script or video of an excursion) to those who were unable to attend the practical sessions in person, ensuring that theoretical knowledge was tested and applied. This resulted in a total of 33 people being certified.

As a lesson learned, the need for companies to continue training was identified, hence the support to obtain the project certificate (Marine Starguide) and join the Atlantic Star Adventures (ASA) product with the support of the project, in addition to the dissemination of the Starlight Foundation process, a quality standard and key entity for continuing training. In addition to the Foundation, we have the regional astronomy groups that participated, such as the Madeira association led by Duarte Oliveira or Astroeduca in the Canary Islands, reinforcing the conclusion that nautical tourism in the ORs is ready to integrate niche experiences that combine maritime culture with science, creating a unique and differentiated product.

BIOACOUSTICS & HYDROPHONES TO CONNECT WITH MARINE WILDLIFE

This training introduced the use of hydrophones in whale watching tours to create immersive, educational acoustic experiences. It responded to high interest expressed during the workshops, though practical integration had been challenging.

- Course Factsheet can be seen in [D2.1 Training Programme Methodology - 2.0](#)
- Registered: 36 people 30 male (83%), 6 female (17%), from 25 enterprises.
- Link to session: [Annex 1. Free access trainings.](#)

Table 12. List of enterprises registered.

ENTERPRISE	TYPE OF STAKEHOLDER	REGION
Aerodream	ENTERPRISE	Martinica
Aquamana Escale Nautik	ENTERPRISE	Martinica
Azores Experiences	ENTERPRISE	Azores
Bleu Caraïbes	ENTERPRISE	Martinica
Caraïbes dauphins	ENTERPRISE	Martinica
Clúster Marítimo de Canarias	ASSOCIATION	Canary Islands
Dolphin and Whales s.l.	ENTERPRISE	Canary Islands
Elittoral S.R.L.	ENTERPRISE	Canary Islands
EISalao	ENTERPRISE	Canary Islands
ULPGC	UNIVERSITY	Canary Islands
InSail	ENTERPRISE	Canary Islands
KR7 ECOTOURS	ENTERPRISE	Madeira
KRISMARA BOAT	ENTERPRISE	Martinica
LA PIROGUE KALINA	ENTERPRISE	Martinica
Madeira Sunkiss Sailing Unip Lda	ENTERPRISE	Madeira
Markùs Évasions	ENTERPRISE	Martinica
Matniknotic	ENTERPRISE	Martinica
Ocean Devotion Madeira	ASSOCIATION	Madeira
OceanEye Azores	ENTERPRISE	Azores
Octopus	ENTERPRISE	Azores
Parc Naturel Régional de la Martinique	ASSOCIATION	Martinica
Prácticos de El Hierro SLP	ENTERPRISE	Canary Islands
São João de Deus	ENTERPRISE	Madeira
SeaEO Tours	ENTERPRISE	Azores
Sud Excursions	ENTERPRISE	Martinica
Terra Azul, Azores Whale Watching	ENTERPRISE	Azores
Terra do Pico - whale watching in Azores	ENTERPRISE	Azores
Wahoo Diving	ENTERPRISE	Azores
Water4fun	ENTERPRISE	Azores

ONLINE SESSION

- Dates: 24th September
- Format: 1,5 hours online session., Spanish with Portuguese subtitles
- [Photos](#)

Figure 19. Hydrophone online session.

- Promotion: through email campaigns, website, partner networks, and social media

Figure 20. Instagram post for Bioacustics training.

MATERIAL

The ppt presentation can be found [here](#).

EXTRA MATERIAL

As a vital component of the hydrophone training course, [BIOACOUSTICS & HYDROPHONES 2](#) instructor Misael Morales Vargas interviewed Robb Nichols, Founder and Product Designer at Aquarian Audio. The interview can be seen in [Annex 2. Extra material](#).

Misael Morales also contributed to our project by providing the Spanish voice-over for the recording "How to be a whale." This recording was originally created by [Tom Muskill](#). For more details, please refer to [Annex 2. Extra material](#).

PRACTICAL PART

A practical session on the 14th of October was organised during the trip to Martinica together with Misael Morales, CEO of BIOSEAN and Jeffrey Bernus, Director and Co-founder of the Caribbean Cetacean Society.

[Signature list](#)

[Photos](#)

CERTIFICATIONS

Certificates were awarded to those who attended the theoretical and/or the practical part.

The certifications were awarded and signed by Sergio Moreno Gil, director of the University Institute of Tourism and Sustainable Economic Development of the University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria, by Matías M. González Hernández, primary researcher of TWINNED by STARS and by Misael Morales Vargas, Director of BIOSEAN and hydrophone instructor.

The certifications can be found in [Annex 3. Certificates](#).

Table 13. Bioacoustics & hydrophones training certifications awarded per region.

Region	People	Male / Female	Enterprises	Associations/Other
Canary Islands	7	71% / 29%	5	2
Azores	10	80% / 20%	8	
Madeira	4	75% / 25%	3	1
Martinica	12	93% / 7%	6	1
TOTAL	33	83% / 17%	22	4

GENDER ANALYSIS

Training in bioacoustics and hydrophones showed the greatest gender disparity from the outset, with predominantly male participation. Of the 36 people registered and certified, 83% were men and only 17% were women. These data reinforce the report's overall conclusion that activities requiring face-to-face attendance or with a more traditional technical focus in the nautical sector remained predominantly male, unlike digital training courses, which were more accessible to women.

CONCLUSIONS TRAINING

This training successfully addressed a high-interest topic by providing a crucial introductory and practical session on integrating hydrophones into whale-watching tours. This training is also noted for its potential to link directly with the project's Atlantic On Board Internships program (AOBI), facilitating practical application of the knowledge gained. The course successfully responded to the high interest expressed by stakeholders during the co-creation workshops regarding the use of hydrophones for creating immersive, educational acoustic experiences, addressing the practical integration challenges previously noted. Furthermore, numerous companies joined the [Atlantic On Board Internships](#) (AOBI) tourism product developed in Work Package 3, confirming the practical application of the knowledge acquired. More info can be found in D3.3 [Report on the product developed including a marketing business plan](#).

In terms of participant demographics, the training attracted substantial interest with 36 people registered from 25 companies, although it showed a marked gender disparity with 83% male participation compared to only 17% female. This distribution is in line with the trend observed in more technical training courses or those requiring attendance at sea.

The training attracted substantial interest, with 36 people registered from 25 enterprises across diverse regions, including the Azores, Canary Islands, Madeira, and Martinica. This broad participation demonstrates the regional relevance and demand for this specialized skill. Supplementary materials, including an interview with a product designer from Aquarian Audio and a Spanish voice-over for an educational recording ("How to be a whale"), enriched the course content. As well as the practical session held in Martinique were two enterprises, one from Azores and one from Madeira could also attend. Furthermore, various enterprises did let us know that they purchased a hydrophone after the training.

Certificates of attendance were formally awarded and signed by representatives from the University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria, the TWINNED by STARS project, and BIOSEAN.

This training is related to the second product that we launched called Atlantic On Board Internships (AOI). The practical and theoretical class on hydrophones served as well to link with enterprises interested in the product.

At the moment of writing of this deliverable, these were the enterprises part of the product or in the process of becoming part of it:

SMEs part of the product:

- BIOSEAN AMBIENTE MARINO S.L (Canary Islands)
- NATURALIST, SCIENCE AND TOURISM (Azores)
- PRACTICOS DE EL HIERRO S.L.P.U. (SEREA) (Canary Islands)
- TERRAAZUL (Azores)
- SEE YOU DIVING (Canary Islands)

SMEs in the process of joining the product:

- DIAJ (Martinica)
- Association Archéologique des Petites Antilles (Martinica)
- Hommes et Femmes à la Barre (Martinica)
- GARA ITSASOA
- ALONDRA ACADEMY

3. CONCLUSIONS

The capacity-building program implemented under WP2 of the TWINNEDbySTARS project successfully achieved its goal of accelerating the digital and ecological transition for nautical tourism SMEs in the ORs. The methodology, based on Design Thinking and co-creation workshops, directly resulted in highly relevant and demand-driven training modules.

All courses, specifically the specialized modules on AI for Social Media, Marine Starguide (Astro-tourism), and Bioacoustics & Hydrophones, were designed in direct response to the needs identified during the local co-creation workshops held in the four ORs. This approach ensured the training provided tools and knowledge immediately applicable to the enterprises' challenges in digital marketing, sustainability, and diversification.

The trainings confirmed a high demand and great relevance of innovation and digitalization tools for nautical tourism SMEs. The "AI for Social Media" course exceeded projections and was the project's most popular offering, demonstrating the urgent need for digital upskilling. Furthermore, the programs maintained solid representation and interest across all four ORs: Azores, Madeira, Canary Islands, and Martinica.

The specialized trainings were instrumental in promoting new lines of sustainable marine ecotourism. A great synergy was created between the courses and the products being developed by TWINNEDbySTARS. Regarding ASA, multiple companies joined the product developed in WP3. Furthermore, the training catalyzed the achievement of external quality standards, with Keep Sailing (Canary Islands) and Madeira Sunkiss Sailing (Madeira) becoming the first nautical companies in their respective regions to obtain the prestigious Starlight Certification. In terms of AOBI, the Bioacoustics course established a direct link with the product, confirming the practical application of acoustic technology in whale-watching tours.

Table 14. Summary of the certified companies and individuals.

Training Course	Total Certified Individuals	Total Certified Enterprises (Unique Count)	Male to female	Key Certification Authority
AI for Social Media	157	63	48%/ 52%	ULPGC-TIDES
Marine Starguide	33	17	79% / 21%	ULPGC-TIDES & Sabadell Astronomy Association
Bioacoustics & Hydrophones	33	22	83% / 17%	ULPGC-TIDES & BIOSEAN
TOTAL	223	102		

In the case of AI for social media, it was a success to use real-world case studies (e.g., Surf Canarias) and *homework* to be done between sessions. In the case of the Marine Starguide course, mandatory practical excursions made the knowledge tangible and immediately implementable.

While interest in digitalization (AI) is high, the perception of its complexity requires ongoing support and simplification. The proactive provision of supplementary guides (like the one for ChatGPT) was an effective immediate response to help enterprises overcome their fear of new technologies.

Regarding participation, data reveals significant gender dynamics, conditioned by the traditionally male-dominated structure of the nautical tourism sector and the format of the courses. In technical and practical training courses, the usual male predominance in the industry was reflected: the Bioacoustics and Hydrophones course had 83% male participation, while in the Marine Starguide course, the gap widened during the process. Although women initially accounted for 28% of registrations, they only constituted 19% of the final certifications. This decrease is attributed to the logistical barriers of the practical sessions, which required travel between islands, making it difficult for female participants to balance their work and personal life.

In contrast, the AI for Social Media course showed a different trend, achieving a majority female participation of 54%. This data suggests that the implementation of 100% online and flexible formats removes barriers to access, facilitating work-life balance and effectively promoting the inclusion and digital training of women in the blue economy. This can also come from a more creative area of social media.

Finally, The project successfully addressed logistical barriers through interpreters and multilingual resources (Spanish, Portuguese, and French materials and interpretation) and flexible certification requirements (e.g., submitting a script or video for the Marine Starguide practical component), ensuring broader participation and knowledge application. While interest in digitalisation (AI) is high, the perception of its complexity requires ongoing support and simplification. The proactive provision of complementary guides (such as ChatGPT) was an immediate and effective response to help businesses overcome their fear of new technologies.

ANNEX 1. FREE ACCESS TRAININGS

All trainings are uploaded on the website for enterprises to check. As this project follows the OA principle, all the trainings will be posted in the YouTube channel, openly accessible after the project end.

Here are the links to all the sessions:

MASTERCLASSES

EXPERIMENTATION AND ONLINE TACTICS TO ATTRACT MORE CUSTOMERS

Date: June 2024

Instructor: Gerard Martínez

- Masterclass experimentação e táticas em linha para atrair novos clientes
Language: [Portuguese](#)
- Masterclass experimentación y tácticas online para atraer a más clientes
Language: [Spanish](#)
- French. Couldn't be recorded in French as there were some technical difficulties.

MASTERCLASS ASTROTOURISM

Date: 20th June 2024

Instructor: Xavier Martínez, from NAUTIC OCEAN

- Masterclass Astroturismo
Language: [Spanish](#)

USE OF AI IN DIGITAL COMMUNICATION FOR NAUTICAL TOURISM

Date Part 1: 18th March 2025

Instructor Part 1: Juan Ma Peral

- [French](#)
- [Portuguese](#)
- [Spanish](#)

Date Part 2: 25th March 2025

Instructor Part 2: Gerard Martínez

- [French](#)
- [Portuguese](#)
- [Spanish](#)

YOUR DIGITAL COMPASS: AI FOR SUCCESSFULLY NAVIGATING SOCIAL MEDIA

Date Part 1: 4th April 2025

Date Part 2: 11th April 2025

Instructor: Raquel Vázquez

- [French Part 1](#)
- [French Part 2](#)
- [Portuguese Part 1](#)
- [Portuguese Part 2](#)
- [Spanish Part 1](#)
- [Spanish Part 2](#)

Notes in:

- [Spanish](#)
- [English](#)

MARINE STARGUIDE

Date: 22nd April 2025

Instructor: Javier Ares

Course: History of Astronomy

- [French](#)
- [Portuguese](#)
- [Spanish](#)

Course: Measuring space-time

- [French](#)
- [Portuguese](#)
- [Spanish](#)

Date: 23rd April 2025

Instructor: Javier Ares

Course: Basic Astronomy Course

- [French](#)
- [Portuguese](#)
- [Spanish](#)

Course: The Solar System

- [French](#)
- [Portuguese](#)
- [Spanish](#)

Date: 24th April 2025

Instructor: Javier Ares

Course: Preparing an observation with Stellarium

- [French](#)
- [Portuguese](#)
- [Spanish](#)

Course: How to orient ourselves in the sky

- [French](#)
- [Portuguese](#)
- [Spanish](#)

Date: 29th April 2025

Instructor: Gerard Martínez

Course: Marketing and public speaking skills

- [French](#)
- [Portuguese](#)
- [Spanish](#)

Date: 30th April 2025

Instructor: Javier Romero, from SEO BIRD LIFE

Course: Light Pollution

- [French](#)
- [Portuguese](#)
- [Spanish](#)

Instructor: Naty Sánchez

Course: Mythology in astronomical navigation

- [French](#)
- [Portuguese](#)
- [Spanish](#)

Date: 7th May 2025

Instructor: Xavier Martínez

Course: History of Navigation

- [French](#)
- [Portuguese](#)
- [Spanish](#)

Couse: Astronomical tourism and the role of certifications

- [French](#)
- [Portuguese](#)

- [Spanish](#)

BIOACOUSTICS & HYDROPHONES TO CONNECT WITH MARINE WILDLIFE

Date: 24th September 2025

Instructor: Misael Morales Vargas, Biosean.

Course: Introduction to bioacoustics and the use of hydrophones for experiments with aquatic fauna

- [Spanish](#)
- [Portuguese](#)

ANNEX 2. EXTRA MATERIAL

CHATGPT GUIDE. PPT VERSION

This guide was developed and shared for enterprises during the [AI for Social Media](#) course.

It was developed in Spanish and translated to French and Portuguese.

- [Link to Spanish version](#)
- [Link to Portuguese version](#)
- [Link to French version](#)

Example in Spanish:

**Cómo usar ChatGPT para que
te ayude a entender cómo
usar ChatGPT en tu
estrategia de comunicación**

Comenzando con ChatGPT

Accede a su web aquí: <https://chatgpt.com/> e inicia sesión para que se guarden las conversaciones.

¿En qué puedo ayudarte?

Pregunta lo que quieras

+ Adjuntar | Buscar | Reason

Analizar datos | Dar consejos | Código | Resumir texto | Dar ideas | Más

Comenzamos: Escribe un prompt. Pero... ¿Qué es un prompt y cómo usarlo para mejorar tu negocio de turismo náutico?

Un **prompt** es el texto que escribimos en el cuadro de diálogo para que ChatGPT nos responda. La calidad de la respuesta depende de lo bien formulado que esté el prompt. Para obtener mejores resultados, sigue estas recomendaciones:

Incluye detalles y contexto

Explica claramente qué necesitas y proporciona información relevante.

Ejemplo: "Actúa como un experto en marketing digital especializado en turismo náutico en Madeira. Quiero estrategias para promocionar mi empresa de excursiones en catamarán en redes sociales."

Usa referencias para la creación de contenido

Puedes incluir ejemplos de publicaciones para que ChatGPT imite el estilo.

Ejemplo: "Escribeme un post para promocionar una clase de surf con un tono similar a este: 'Así de bien lo estamos pasando este verano 🌊🏄‍♀️🌴️ Aún quedan plazas en agosto... ¡No se lo pierdan!'"

Divide las solicitudes en pasos

No pidas todo en un solo prompt. Primero solicita una estrategia general, luego ejemplos de contenido, después mejoras en el tono, etc.

Recuerda que ChatGPT puede perder el hilo

En cada nuevo prompt, refuerza el contexto.

Si algo no cuadra en la respuesta, pídele que justifique su respuesta con preguntas como: "¿En qué te basas para decir eso?" o "¿Qué evidencia respalda tu respuesta?"

Comenzando con un Prompt Básico

Escribe un prompt para comenzar a investigar el mundo de ChatGPT y cómo puede ayudarte en la comunicación digital.

¿En qué puedo ayudarte?

Soy una empresa de Canarias de Surf, en concreto SurfCanarias, me gustaría poder mejorar mi comunicación digital contigo. ¿Me puedes decir cómo puedo usarlo para ello?

+ Adjuntar | Buscar | Reason

Analizar datos | Dar consejos | Código | Resumir texto | Dar ideas | Más

Prompt básico

Respuesta al Prompt Básico

¡Genial! Como SurfCanaries, puedes usar me para mejorar tu comunicación digital en varias áreas clave. Aquí te dejo algunas formas concretas en las que puedo ayudarte:

- Creación de Contenido para Redes Sociales**
 - Generar textos atractivos para publicaciones en Instagram, Facebook y TikTok.
 - Ideas de contenido: Reels con mini-tutoriales de surf. Preguntas y respuestas sobre el mejor equipo o spots en Canarias. Historias destacadas con testimonios de alumnos.
 - Ejemplo de copy para Instagram: "🌊 ¿Primer día en el agua? Aquí van 3 tips para mantenerte en la tabla más tiempo. Swipe 📖 y dínos cuál ya conocías. 🌊 #SurfCanarias"
- Optimización de SEO para Atraer Más Clientes**
 - Mejorar los textos de tu web para que Google te posicione mejor.
 - Encontrar palabras clave para que más turistas y locales encuentren tus clases de surf.
 - Sugerencias para títulos SEO: "Las mejores playas para aprender a surfear en Canarias 🌊" "Surf para principiantes en [nombre de tu zona]"
- Análisis de Datos con Metricool o Google Analytics**
 - Te ayudo a interpretar tus métricas de redes sociales y tráfico web.
 - Puedes pegarme los datos y te daré recomendaciones para mejorar tu alcance.
- Automatización y Respuesta a Clientes**
 - Generar respuestas rápidas para preguntas frecuentes en WhatsApp o Instagram.
 - Ejemplo de respuesta automatizada: "¡Hola! 🌊 Nuestras clases de surf están disponibles todos los días. ¿Qué nivel tienes? Puedes reservar aquí: [link]"
- Creación de un Calendario de Contenidos**
 - Te ayudo a planificar publicaciones semanales o mensuales.
 - Puedo sugerir eventos temáticos, challenges o promociones para mantener el interés. 🌟 Si quieres, dime en qué área quieres enfocarte primero y empezamos a trabajar en ello. 🌊

Mejorando el Prompt

Esto era... ¿muy básico verdad?

Queremos saber más, qué ofrece y cómo podemos beneficiarnos, paso a paso. Así que podemos ir pidiéndole que nos diga más sobre uno de los aspectos o podemos **utilizar un prompt más específico** como este:

"Soy SurfCanaries, una empresa de surf en Canarias. Quiero mejorar mi comunicación digital y aprovechar al máximo ChatGPT para ello. ¿Puedes explicarme cómo utilizarlo para mejorar mis redes sociales, crear contenido atractivo y optimizar mi web? Dame un plan paso a paso con ejemplos"

Tip: ¡también puedes preguntarle a ChatGPT cómo mejorar el prompt!

Respuesta Mejorada: Redes Sociales

Obtendrás una respuesta como esta (se vienen varias diapositivas):

1 Mejorar tu Comunicación en Redes Sociales

Paso 1: Crear un Calendario de Publicaciones

- **Frecuencia de publicación:** Decide cuántas veces al día o a la semana vas a publicar (por ejemplo, 3 publicaciones por semana en Instagram/Facebook).
- **Tipos de contenido:**
 - ✓ Reels y vídeos cortos mostrando clases, trucos y surfistas disfrutando.
 - ✓ Historias con contenido diario (tipos de olas, equipo de surf, detrás de cámaras).
 - ✓ Post educativos sobre cómo mejorar en el surf.
 - ✓ Testimonios de clientes y fotos de grupos.
- ChatGPT puede ayudarte a generar ideas de contenido y hasta crear el texto de cada publicación.

Ejemplo:

👋🏽 ¡Hoy en SurfCanaries! Aprendemos a dominar las olas. Aquí van 3 tips para mejorar tu postura en la tabla de surf. Desliza para más detalles 📖

Paso 2: Generar Contenido Atractivo

- **Post sobre lecciones de surf:**
 - "¡Comienza tu aventura en el surf con nosotros! 🌊 Primeros pasos, equipo necesario y las mejores playas de Canarias para surfear. Reserva tu clase hoy mismo: [enlace]"
- **Historias interactivas:** Usa encuestas o preguntas como:
 - "¿Listo para surfear en Canarias? ¿Qué playa prefieres? 🏖️"
- **Reels con trucos:** "¡Mira cómo surfear la ola perfecta en Playa de Las Canteras! 🏽 ¿Te animas a hacerlo?"

Paso 3: Usar ChatGPT para Programar y Crear Texto

- ChatGPT puede generar **captions** para tus posts, sugerir **hashtags** populares relacionados con el surf y las Islas Canarias, y crear textos atractivos para **historias de Instagram**. Además, te ayuda a mantener la voz de tu marca consistente.

Respuesta Mejorada: Optimización Web

1 Optimizar tu Web para SEO

Paso 1: Analizar Palabras Clave para Atraer Más Tráfico

- **SEO para SurfCanaries:** Usa herramientas como Google Keyword Planner para encontrar las palabras clave más relevantes.
- **Ejemplo de palabras clave:** "surf en Canarias", "clases de surf en Gran Canaria", "mejores playas para surfear", "surf principiantes Canarias".
- ChatGPT puede ayudarte a crear contenido optimizado usando estas palabras clave. Puedes mejorar los textos de tu web para que los usuarios encuentren más fácilmente tu página.

Ejemplo:

¿Nuevo en el surf? ¡Te enseñamos desde cero en las mejores playas de Canarias! Descubre las clases para principiantes en SurfCanaries y empieza hoy mismo. 🌊🏽

Paso 2: Mejorar la Usabilidad y Experiencia de Usuario

- Asegúrate de que la página de reservas sea fácil de navegar y cargue rápidamente.
- ChatGPT te puede ayudar a generar mensajes de bienvenida o FAQ (preguntas frecuentes) que optimicen la navegación.

Ejemplo de mensaje de bienvenida:

¡Bienvenido a SurfCanaries! Reserva tu clase de surf en solo 3 clics y prepárate para conquistar las olas. 🌊

Paso 3: Crear Blogs y Artículos

- Genera **blogs informativos** relacionados con el surf.
- **Ideas de artículos:** "Cómo elegir la mejor tabla de surf para principiantes", "Top 5 playas de Canarias para surfistas avanzados", "Consejos para surfear en invierno".
- ChatGPT puede ayudarte a crear estos artículos, optimizados para SEO, y a programar publicaciones en tu blog.

Respuesta Mejorada: Análisis de Datos

3 Analizar Datos y Ajustar Estrategias

Paso 1: Revisa tus Métricas de Redes Sociales y Web

- Usa herramientas como **Google Analytics** y **Metricool** para ver qué contenido está funcionando mejor.
- **Métricas clave:** Tasa de conversión, tiempo en página, clics en la página de reservas, interacciones en redes sociales, etc.

Paso 2: Ajusta tu Estrategia de Contenido

- Si las publicaciones de **tutoriales de surf** están generando muchas interacciones, planea más contenido educativo.
- Si las **historias de clientes** tienen más engagement, crea más publicaciones que muestren a los surfistas disfrutando de las clases.

Paso 3: Usa ChatGPT para Ajustar el Mensaje

- Basándote en las métricas, **ajusta los mensajes** de tus publicaciones. Si notas que tu público responde mejor a contenido **emocional** (como disfrutar de la libertad en el mar), enfócate más en esa dirección.

Ejemplo:

"Nada como la sensación de estar sobre una ola, ¿verdad? 🌊 No solo surfearás, sino que vivirás una experiencia inolvidable. Reserva ahora y empieza tu aventura. 🏄"

Resumen del Plan de Acción

¡ChatGPT te da hasta un resumen!

1

Redes Sociales

Utiliza ChatGPT para **crear contenido** diario (Reels, posts, historias) que conecte con tu audiencia.

2

SEO Web

Optimiza tu web con **palabras clave** relacionadas con el surf y crea contenido de valor para mejorar tu posicionamiento.

3

Análisis de Datos

Revisa **métricas** de redes y web y **ajusta tu estrategia** de contenido basándote en los resultados.

Bastante completa la respuesta, ¿verdad?

En cada parte que no entendamos podemos volver a preguntarle a ChatGPT e ir desgranando uno a uno todos los apartados y sus pasos.

Ejemplos de Prompts Específicos

Aquí tienes otros ejemplos de prompts específicos para empresas de turismo náutico en Canarias, Azores, Madeira y Martinica

Estrategia de marketing digital

"Actúa como un consultor de marketing digital especializado en turismo náutico en Azores. ¿Cómo puedo diferenciar mis excursiones de avistamiento de cetáceos en un mercado competitivo?"

Creación de contenido para redes sociales

"Genera un post de Instagram para promocionar una experiencia de buceo en Madeira. Usa un tono aventurero y enfatiza la biodiversidad marina."

Atención al cliente y ventas

"Redacta respuestas para clientes interesados en alquilar veleros en Martinica. Quiero respuestas que resalten la comodidad y exclusividad de la experiencia."

Sostenibilidad y ecoturismo

"Crea un mensaje para mi página web sobre el compromiso de mi empresa de excursiones en kayak en Canarias con el turismo sostenible."

Optimización de sitio web

"Hazme una lista de palabras clave para mejorar el SEO de mi web de turismo náutico en Madeira, centrada en paddle surf y travesías en kayak."

¡Eso es todo!

¿Ha sido útil?

Te animamos a embarcarte en el mundo de ChatGPT, investigar e ir probando. Puedes empezar usando estos prompts y adaptándolos a tu empresa.

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CHATGPT GUIDE. WORD VERSION

Here is the guide in English as a Word version:

Open ChatGPT. Here: <https://chatgpt.com/> Log in so your conversations are saved.

Let's begin:

Write a prompt.

What is a prompt and how do you use it to improve your nautical tourism business?

A prompt is the text we write in the dialogue box for ChatGPT to answer us. The quality of the answer depends on how well-formulated the prompt is.

To get better results, follow these recommendations:

1. **Include details and context:** Explain clearly what you need and provide relevant information.
 - o *Example:* "Act as a digital marketing expert specializing in nautical tourism in [Canary Islands, Azores, Madeira, or Martinique]. I want strategies to promote my catamaran excursion company on social media."
2. **Divide requests into steps:** Don't ask for everything in a single prompt. First ask for a general strategy, then content examples, then tone improvements, etc.
3. **Use references for content creation:** You can include examples of posts for ChatGPT to imitate the style.
 - o *Example:* "Write me a post to promote a surf class with a tone similar to this: 'We are having such a great time this summer 🌞🏄🌴 There are still spots left in August... Don't miss out!'"
4. **Remember that ChatGPT can lose the thread:** In every new prompt, reinforce the context. If something doesn't add up in the answer, ask it to justify its response with questions like: "What do you base that on?" or "What evidence supports your answer?"

Write a prompt to start investigating the world of ChatGPT and how it can help you in digital communication.

Example of a response with a basic prompt like this:

"I am a surf company from the Canary Islands, specifically SurfCanaries, and I would like to improve my digital communication with you. Can you tell me how I can use you for this?"

RESPONSE:

Great! As SurfCanaries, you can use me to improve your digital communication in several key areas. Here are some specific ways I can help you:

1 Social Media Content Creation Generate attractive texts for posts on Instagram, Facebook, and TikTok.

- Content ideas:
 - Reels with surf mini-tutorials.
 - Q&A about the best gear or spots in the Canary Islands.
 - Highlight stories with student testimonials.
- Example of Instagram copy: "🏄 First day in the water? Here are 3 tips to stay on the board longer. Swipe 👉 and tell us which one you already knew. 🌊 #SurfCanaries"

2 SEO Optimization to Attract More Customers

- Improve your website texts so Google ranks you better.
- Find keywords so more tourists and locals find your surf classes.
- Suggestions for SEO titles:
 - "The best beaches to learn surfing in the Canary Islands 🌊"
 - "Surfing for beginners in [name of your area]"

3 Data Analysis with Metricool or Google Analytics

- I help you interpret your social media and web traffic metrics.
- You can paste the data, and I will give you recommendations to improve your reach.

4 Automation and Customer Response

- Generate quick responses for frequently asked questions on WhatsApp or Instagram.
- Example of automated response: "Hello! 🏄 Our surf classes are available every day. What is your level? You can book here: [link]"

5 Creating a Content Calendar

- I help you plan weekly or monthly publications.
- I can suggest thematic events, challenges, or promotions to maintain interest.

🚀 *If you want, tell me which area you want to focus on first and we can start working on it.* 🔄

Moving to Advanced Prompts

Very basic, right? We want to know more. We can ask for the step-by-step of each one, or use a more specific prompt like this:

"I am SurfCanaries, a surf company in the Canary Islands. I want to improve my digital communication and make the most of ChatGPT for it. Can you explain how to use you to improve my social media, create attractive content, and optimize my website? Give me a step-by-step plan with examples."

(Tip: You can also ask ChatGPT how to improve the prompt)

You will get a response like this:

1 Improve your Communication on Social Media

Step 1: Create a Posting Calendar

- Posting frequency: Decide how many times a day or week you are going to post (e.g., 3 posts per week on Instagram/Facebook).
- Content types:
 - Reels and short videos showing classes, tricks, and surfers enjoying themselves.
 - Stories with daily content (types of waves, surf gear, behind the scenes).
 - Educational posts on how to improve surfing.
 - Testimonials from clients and group photos.
- ChatGPT can help you generate content ideas and even create the text for each post.
 - *Example: "🏄‍♂️ ✨ Today at SurfCanaries! We learn to master the waves. Here are 3 tips to improve your stance on the surfboard. Swipe for more details 👉"*

Step 2: Generate Attractive Content

- Post about surf lessons: "Start your surf adventure with us! 🔄 First steps, necessary gear, and the best beaches in the Canary Islands to surf. Book your class today: [link]"

- Interactive Stories: Use polls or questions like: "Ready to surf in the Canary Islands? Which beach do you prefer? 🏄"
- Reels with tricks: "Watch how we surf the perfect wave at Playa de Las Canteras! 🔥 Dare to try it?"

Step 3: Use ChatGPT to Schedule and Create Text

- ChatGPT can generate captions for your posts, suggest popular hashtags related to surfing and the Canary Islands, and create attractive texts for Instagram Stories.
- Additionally, it helps you keep your brand voice consistent.

2 Optimize your Web for SEO

Step 1: Analyze Keywords to Attract More Traffic

- SEO for SurfCanaries: Use tools like Google Keyword Planner to find the most relevant keywords.
- Example keywords: "surf in Canary Islands", "surf lessons in Gran Canaria", "best beaches to surf", "beginner surf Canary Islands".
- ChatGPT can help you create optimized content using these keywords. You can improve your website texts so users find your page more easily.
 - *Example:* "New to surfing? We teach you from scratch at the best beaches in the Canary Islands! Discover beginner classes at SurfCanaries and start today. 🌊🏄"

Step 2: Improve Usability and User Experience

- Ensure the booking page is easy to navigate and loads quickly.
- ChatGPT can help you generate welcome messages or FAQ (frequently asked questions) that optimize navigation.
 - *Example welcome message:* "Welcome to SurfCanaries! Book your surf class in just 3 clicks and get ready to conquer the waves. 🌊"

Step 3: Create Blogs and Articles

- Generate informative blogs related to surfing.
- Article ideas: "How to choose the best surfboard for beginners", "Top 5 beaches in the Canary Islands for advanced surfers", "Tips for surfing in winter".
- ChatGPT can help you create these articles, optimized for SEO, and schedule posts on your blog.

3 Analyze Data and Adjust Strategies

Step 1: Review your Social Media and Web Metrics

- Use tools like Google Analytics and Metricool to see what content is working best.

- Key metrics: Conversion rate, time on page, clicks on the booking page, interactions on social media, etc.

Step 2: Adjust your Content Strategy

- If surf tutorial posts are generating many interactions, plan more educational content.
- If client stories have more engagement, create more posts showing surfers enjoying the classes.

Step 3: Use ChatGPT to Adjust the Message

- Based on the metrics, adjust the messages of your posts.
- If you notice your audience responds better to emotional content (like enjoying freedom in the sea), focus more in that direction.
 - *Example:* "Nothing like the feeling of being on a wave, right? 🌊 You won't just surf, you'll live an unforgettable experience. Book now and start your adventure. 🏄"

Action Plan Summary

- Social Media: Use ChatGPT to create daily content (Reels, posts, stories) that connects with your audience.
- Web SEO: Optimize your web with keywords related to surfing and create valuable content to improve your ranking.
- Data Analysis: Review network and web metrics and adjust your content strategy based on the results.

Quite complete, right? In every part we don't understand, we can ask ChatGPT again and break down all the sections and their steps one by one.

Other examples of specific prompts for nautical tourism companies in the Canary Islands, Azores, Madeira, and Martinique

1. **Digital Marketing Strategy:** "Act as a digital marketing consultant specializing in nautical tourism in the Azores. How can I differentiate my whale watching excursions in a competitive market?"
2. **Social Media Content Creation:** "Generate an Instagram post to promote a diving experience in Madeira. Use an adventurous tone and emphasize marine biodiversity."
3. **Customer Service and Sales:** "Draft responses for customers interested in renting sailboats in Martinique. I want answers that highlight the comfort and exclusivity of the experience."
4. **Sustainability and Ecotourism:** "Create a message for my website about my kayak excursion company's commitment to sustainable tourism in the Canary Islands."
5. **Website Optimization:** "Make me a list of keywords to improve the SEO of my nautical tourism website in Madeira, focused on paddle surf and kayak crossings."

SCRIPT FOR PRACTICAL PART MARINE STARGUIDE

A script was developed between NAUTIC OCEAN and KEEP SAILING for the first FAM TRIP organised.

- [20th of March](#), Gran Canaria
- [15th June](#), Sao Miguel
- [1st of October](#), Gran Canaria
- [14th October](#), Martinica

This script was designed for the "Keep Sailing Astrotourism Experience 2025," a two-hour nautical excursion departing from Pasito Blanco, Gran Canaria, on March 20th, 2025 and then re-used for the practical parts as an example to follow. The trip, limited to 12 participants per vessel, is designed as a courtesy FAM TRIP to promote Keep Sailing as the first Starlight-certified nautical tourism company in the Canary Islands, as part of the TWINNEDbySTARS project. The script is divided into three phases: it begins with a focus on the sunset and the connection to space, featuring the historical role of the Maspalomas Space Station in the Apollo 11 mission, and astronomical lessons on the equinox, the Point of Aries, and the planets Venus and Mercury, interwoven with Greco-Latin and Guanche mythology. The second phase focuses on celestial navigation, explaining the historical shift from using the coastline and winds to utilizing the compass, understanding magnetic declination, and using Polaris to determine latitude, alongside star-hopping techniques and Canarian star legends like Tigotán. The experience concludes with a moment of contemplation and a toast before returning to port, where guests are invited to an extended observation session using a Seestar S50 telescope to view deep-sky objects like the Orion Nebula and the Pleiades.

INTERVIEW WITH ROBB NICHOLS: HYDROPHONES TO CONNECT AND PROTECT MARINE WILDLIFE

Part of the hydrophone training course, "[Bioacoustics & Hydrophones to Connect with Marine Wildlife](#)," instructor Misael Morales Vargas speaks with Robb Nichols, Founder and Product Designer at Aquarian Audio.

Nichols, who has dedicated 27 years to democratizing access to hydrophones and promoting awareness of marine sustainability, shares how his passion for sound and the ocean led him to create devices accessible to anyone interested in exploring and protecting aquatic ecosystems.

Key Topics Covered: The beginnings of Aquarian Audio, the creation of the first homemade hydrophone, the applications of these sensors in conservation, aquaculture, and engineering, and Nichols' vision for the democratization of technology and citizen participation in ocean protection.

Watch the interview here: <https://youtu.be/bnGEpsrbUGE?si=3dm4lwSa6x8F2S90>

HOW TO BE A WHALE

"[How to be a Whale](#)" is a thirty-minute audio, described as a bioacoustic listening journey. This sound experience explores the history of marine mammals through the lives of seven different species of whales and dolphins.

It was originally created by wildlife filmmaker Tom Mustill and "Whale DJ" Vahakn Matossian, with support from the charity WDC (Whale and Dolphin Conservation), and released for free for World Ocean Day.

Misael Morales Vargas, instructor for our bioacoustic training and CEO of Biosean (an SME within the TWINNEDbySTARS project), shared the [Spanish version](#) of the audio with the project, for which he provided the voice-over.

ANNEX 3. CERTIFICATES

The diplomas have been signed and distributed. In accordance to the Data Protection Law, we will only share the templates created:

AI FOR SOCIAL MEDIA

- [Template:](#)

“IA PARA LA COMUNICACIÓN DIGITAL Y LA AUTOMATIZACIÓN DE CAMPAÑAS EN REDES SOCIALES”

Temario	HORAS
TEMA 1 Introducción a la IA en Marketing Digital	1
TEMA 2 Herramientas y Automatización de Campañas	1
TEMA 3 Estrategias de Optimización y Personalización	1
TEMA 4 Introducción y aplicación básica de <u>ChatGPT</u>	1
TEMA 5 Definición de una estrategia digital	1
TEMA 6 Optimización y automatización de procesos	1

“IA PARA LA COMUNICACIÓN DIGITAL Y LA AUTOMATIZACIÓN DE CAMPAÑAS EN REDES SOCIALES”:

CALIFICACIÓN OBTENIDA: CALIFICACIÓN

MARINE STARGUIDE

- [Template](#)

Instituto Universitario de
Turismo y Desarrollo
Económico Sostenible

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DIPLOMA

La Universidad de Las Palmas de Gran Canaria y la Asociación Astronómica de Sabadell hace constar que

XXXXX

ha completado con éxito el Curso

Marine Starguide

Gran Canaria, 11 de noviembre de 2025

Sergio Moreno Gil

Director Instituto TIDES

Matías M. González Hernández

Coordinador Proyecto TWINNED by STARS

Carles Schnabel

Presidente Agrupación Astronómica de Sabadell

PROGRAMA FORMATIVO “MARINE STARGUIDE”

PLAN DE ESTUDIOS

Asignaturas	HORAS
ASIGNATURA 1 Historia de la Astronomía	1,5
ASIGNATURA 2 Medir El Espacio Tiempo	1,5
ASIGNATURA 3 Curso Básico De Astronomía	1,5
ASIGNATURA 4 El Sistema Solar	1,5
ASIGNATURA 5 Cómo Orientamos En El Cielo	1,5
ASIGNATURA 6 Preparar Una Observación con <u>Stellarium</u>	1,5
ASIGNATURA 7 Historia De La Navegación	2
ASIGNATURA 8 El Turismo Astronómico Y El Papel De Las Certificaciones	1
ASIGNATURA 9 Marketing Astroturismo Náutico Y Habilidades De Comunicación En Oratorias	3
ASIGNATURA 10 Contaminación Lumínica	1
ASIGNATURA 11 Mitología En La Navegación Astronómica	2
ASIGNATURA 12 Salida al mar, parte práctica	3

PROGRAMA FORMATIVO “MARINE STARGUIDE”:

CALIFICACIÓN OBTENIDA: CALIFICACIÓN

BIOACOUSTICS & HYDROPHONES TO CONNECT WITH MARINE WILDLIFE

- [Template:](#)

Instituto Universitario de
Turismo y Desarrollo
Económico Sostenible

Co-funded by
the European Union

DIPLOMA

XXXXX

ha completado con éxito el curso:

Introducción a la Bioacústica y al Uso de Hidrófonos para Experiencias
con Fauna Acuática

Gran Canaria, 11 de noviembre de 2025

Sergio Moreno Gil

Director Instituto TIDES

Matías M. González Hernández

Coordinador Proyecto
TWINNED by STARS

Misael Morales Vargas

Director BIOSEAN
Whale Watching & Marine Science

CONTENIDO DEL CURSO

	HORAS
FUNDAMENTOS DE LA BIOACÚSTICA APLICADA AL TURISMO ACUÁTICO	0,22
BIOLOGÍA, MEDIOAMBIENTE Y ESPECIES OBSERVADAS EN TENERIFE	0,22
FACTORES ACÚSTICOS Y LA EXPERIENCIA CON HIDRÓFONOS	0,22
TECNOLOGÍA Y FUNCIONAMIENTO DE LOS HIDRÓFONOS. ASPECTOS TÉCNICOS	0,22
METODOLOGÍAS DE EXPERIENCIAS ACÚSTICAS CON FAUNA	0,22
APLICACIONES Y CASOS PRÁCTICOS EN CONSERVACIÓN Y MONITOREO	0,22
STORYTELLING Y CONSEJOS PRÁCTICOS PARA GUÍAS DE TURISMO MARINO	0,22

CALIFICACIÓN OBTENIDA: CALIFICACIÓN

TWINNED

By Stars

Unlocking the potential of innovation, circularity, and digitalisation for accelerating new marine-based ecotourism, joint practices, and businesses in ORs

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